

METHODOLOGICAL FEATURES OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN THE ERA OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

Nasrullaev Odil Kutbitdinovich

senior teacher

E-mail: odilnasrullaev@gmail.com

University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences

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Learning in the digital age is about a deeper transformation of the entire learning process, using new digital tools to rethink how learning needs to be modern. Technological innovations in the information environment make it possible to expand learning opportunities through a combination of traditional teaching methods and modern technologies.

In order to accelerate the development of the digital industry in Uzbekistan, increase the competitiveness of the national economy, as well as ensure the implementation of the tasks defined in the State Program for the Implementation of the Action Strategy for five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017 - 2021 in the “Year of Development of Science, Education and Digital Economy” ", the Strategy "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" was approved [1].

The importance of further digitalization of the economy of Uzbekistan was noted in the January 2020 Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. The head of our state identified an active transition to the digital economy as one of the main priorities for the next five years. “For sustainable development, we must deeply master digital knowledge and information technology, which will enable us to take the shortest path to achieving comprehensive progress. In the modern world, digital technologies play a decisive role in all spheres..... Modern information technologies must be introduced at all stages of the education system” [2].

In the program for the development of the digital economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the issue of training personnel for the education system is included

as one of the main factors. It identifies the following key areas of human resources and education:

- personal technology training;
- creating an education system that can train specialists with deep knowledge in these areas;
- training of highly qualified specialists in higher education;
- creation of modern scientific and practical literature, which is necessary for a comprehensive study of the digital economy;
- development of labor market mechanisms;
- creation of national ecosystems in various sectors of the economy using electronic platform technologies.

Therefore, a digital economy program has been created and is being successfully implemented in our republic. The most important measure of digitalization of education was the training of qualified personnel and the creation of digital information infrastructure. Therefore, each university teacher developed his or her own roadmap, which was of great interest to education.

In the conditions of modern social, scientific and technological progress, the widespread development of all branches of science and technology, particularly high demands are placed on improving the educational process in higher education and the quality of training of graduating specialists. In this regard, teaching English in universities of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as a language of international communication, is of particular importance. In a non-linguistic university, English serves not only as a means of communication, but also as a means of cognition; it should become the main means for students to obtain scientific information, a means of active inclusion in the sphere of science, production and public life.

Digital technologies have become an integral part of our lives, including such areas as learning foreign languages. Information technologies and digital tools in teaching foreign languages are becoming increasingly significant and widely used in education throughout the world, including the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Universities today have a responsibility to teach students how to get the most out of digital technologies in their learning. Institutions that develop the right learning strategies can open up many new and exciting opportunities to engage with students and faculty. There is no one way to achieve specific results using digital technologies. By giving individual educators, the opportunity to try new ways of working with digital technologies, and providing them with the support they need, a college of education can become a dynamic institution with its own digital identity. Taking advantage of the digital age is up to each teacher.

At the same time, digitalization in itself is not a methodological approach, but can only help in the implementation of existing methods and offer new types of activities within the framework of these methods. Modern information, communication and digital technologies make it possible to combine text, graphic and video images, speech and music in digital form. Based on digital technologies, powerful innovative means of accumulating, presenting and transmitting knowledge, as well as learning tools, are being created [3].

In the implementation of these tasks, paramount importance belongs to the improvement of methods and means of teaching in universities on the basis of modern achievements of science and technology, theory and teaching practice. A significant role in solving these problems belongs to the use of digital technologies, which are increasingly used at all levels of education. The use of digital technologies in the educational process of universities will enrich students with new ways of perceiving information, speed up the process of acquiring knowledge, improve their quality, and improve their professional training. And, accordingly, secondary and higher schools are faced with the task of improving the methodology for using the most promising and advanced technical teaching aids.

Digitalization in itself will not change anything, because it is not a methodological approach, but can only help in the implementation of existing didactic micro- and macro-methods and, if necessary, offer new activities within these methods. Hoping that technological progress will fundamentally change the educational landscape is counterproductive: if only the technical means are

changed, no real development will occur. Modern digital technologies can support any approaches and methods of teaching foreign languages. Therefore, digitalization can be used with equal success both to create new and improve existing approaches, and if we continue to follow modern methodological eclecticism [4].

In recent years, the use of digital technologies in teaching foreign languages has become increasingly widespread. With the rapid development of technology, both teachers and students have realized the potential benefits that digital tools can bring to language acquisition. However, like any other tool, digital technology has its pros and cons. In this article we will look at the pros and cons of using digital technology in language learning.

Transformation in foreign language teaching will become a reality if teaching and learning practices are completely changed, if habitual behavioral patterns are abandoned and a new program is developed. Without the active participation of all parties in the educational process, these transformations are impossible.

As we know, digital technologies are tools that help students and teachers develop learning capabilities, reform the organization of classes, and provide support for any educational and methodological resources both in the classroom and outside it. When preparing for classes and during classes, teacher can widely use such a variety of Internet resources as: email, online whiteboard, video conferencing, interactive videos, assignments in Moodle, webinars.

We are confident that change will come. In any case, gradual changes will occur, especially in the areas of classroom management and the development of teaching tools that can be used for individual learning, both inside and outside the classroom. The use of digital tools will change the organization of teaching and learning. Digital classroom registers, software for organizing and administering exams, software systems for managing administrative processes in educational institutions, platforms that provide teaching and learning materials and support educational processes will become widespread, if not universal, in the future. This

will allow more data to be collected about students and how they learn and research on language teaching and learning will be able to build on these data sets, leading to new understanding and rethinking in certain areas.

This information will be used to create adaptive learning materials that enable personalized learning. Access to materials and opportunities for virtual communication in the target language will be further simplified; multimodality of means will increase and differentiate. In addition, the number of free methodological and educational materials will continue to grow.

The use of digital technologies in teaching foreign languages provides a number of advantages. First, they provide students with access to a wide range of authentic materials, such as videos, podcasts and online articles, which can improve their language skills and cultural understanding. Additionally, digital tools allow students to practice their language skills in an interactive and fun way through online exercises, language learning apps, and virtual language exchange platforms. These platforms often provide instant feedback, allowing students to track their progress and identify areas for improvement. Additionally, digital technologies provide flexibility in time and location, allowing learners to study at their own pace [5].

One of the main advantages of digital technologies in language learning is their accessibility. Thanks to the Internet and mobile devices, students can access language learning resources anytime, anywhere. This means that you no longer have to rely solely on textbooks or physical classrooms to learn a language. They can access online courses, language learning apps, and interactive sites that offer a wide range of language learning materials. This accessibility allows students to practice their language skills at their own pace, making learning more flexible and personalized. Another advantage of digital technologies in language learning is their interactivity [6].

Many language learning apps and websites contain interactive exercises, tests, and games that engage students and make learning more enjoyable. However, there are also potential disadvantages to using digital technologies in language

learning. Firstly, dependence on digital technologies can lead to a reduction in face-to-face communication, which is very important for the development of speaking and listening skills. Additionally, excessive use of technology can lead to poor concentration as students can be easily distracted by other online activities. It should be noted that not all students have equal access to digital technologies, which can create a digital divide and limit some people's ability to access language learning resources.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the use of digital technologies in teaching foreign languages has both advantages and disadvantages. Digital tools provide students with access to authentic content, interactive exercises, and flexibility, but they can also interfere with face-to-face interactions and distract from learning.

To sum up, it is important for teachers and students to find a balance between the use of digital technologies and traditional teaching methods to ensure meaningful language learning. The use of digital technologies in teaching foreign languages has both pros and cons. The accessibility, interactivity, and exposure to authentic language resources that digital technologies provide can greatly enhance language learning opportunities. However, students should be aware of the possible distractions and limitations of digital tools and seek a balance between online and offline learning activities.

Ultimately, the effectiveness of using digital technologies in the study of foreign languages depends on how they are used and integrated into a comprehensive foreign language teaching program.

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